

APPLICATION OF TIME-FREQUENCY ANALYSIS TO MACHINERY CONDITION ASSESSMENT

Robert A. Rohrbaugh

*Advanced Signal Processing Branch (Code 734)
Naval Surface Warfare Center Carderock Division
Detachment Puget Sound
Bremerton, WA 98314-5215*

Abstract

Machinery condition has traditionally been assessed by analysis of the spectral energy density of the machine's vibration signal. Examination of time-frequency representations (TFRs) of constant-speed machinery data reveals vibration features that demonstrate variation in frequency over a short time period and thus cannot be adequately characterized by the power spectrum. These features may be used as supplemental information to assess the condition of the machine. Although the spectrogram provides a general indication of the time-varying spectrum, new representations such as the "cone-kernel" TFR reveal the existence of fine structural details inherent to the signal.

Introduction

Condition assessment of constant-speed machinery has benefitted considerably from methods based on analysis of the spectral energy density. Although time-domain analysis is occasionally used to diagnose problems that are characterized by amplitude modulation of the signal, modern preventive maintenance programs depend upon frequency-domain methods to determine the condition of constant-speed machines.

Machinery condition is normally assessed by observing the presence of assumed stationary frequency components, noting the amplitude of these frequency components with respect to a reference vibration level, and comparing the levels of these components with those of previously acquired spectra. The machinery analyst may then gain insight into various physical characteristics of the machine. For example, the presence of certain frequency components not usually seen in the spectrum of a machine may indicate degradation of a bearing, or a relatively high-level rotational component may signify that the shaft is out of balance. If the amplitude of a certain frequency component exceeds a predetermined threshold, the analyst may determine that maintenance action is warranted for the machine.

Analysis of the power spectrum has proven to be effective at identifying many problems associated with

constant-speed machines including balance, alignment, pump pulsation, pulley, impeller, and gear deficiencies. However, identification of bearing problems is somewhat more difficult due to the physical nature of bearing defects. Bearing problems may be complex in nature and are identified by increases in broadband noise levels and rotational harmonics, modulation of other component frequencies, or increases of certain discrete tones. These tones are related to the cage, raceways, and rolling elements of the bearing.

In addition to bearing-related problems, power spectral analysis may not provide sufficient insight to uniquely identify other machinery problems. Pulley assemblies, pistons, impellers, or other components that vibrate near bearing-related frequencies or machine resonance frequencies may impede proper analysis. Cavitation may be mistaken for broadband noise levels that often result from bearing degradation. High frequency discrete tones in turbines may be gear or steam-related. Specific tones and entire bands of energy have been observed to vary in amplitude over short periods of time.

If all frequencies present in a signal exist for the entire duration of the signal, analysis of the stationary spectral energy density is sufficient to describe the frequency composition. Since the spectrum of a constant-speed machine would be expected to consist of stationary frequency components, variation of these components over time may indicate a developing problem.

Background

For the case of general machinery applications, a TFR is desired that allows inspection of short and long-duration transients while preserving narrowband analysis capability. Perhaps the most common method of analyzing the time-varying spectrum is by means of the spectrogram, which was originally developed for speech analysis. To calculate the spectrogram, a finite analysis window, $h(t')$, is applied to a signal $s(t)$ at time t , and the magnitude-squared value of the Fourier transform of the window segment is computed:

$$\text{TFR}_{\text{SPEC}}(t, f) = \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} s(t') h^*(t-t') e^{-j2\pi f t'} dt' \right|^2 \quad (1)$$

where * denotes complex conjugation.

For many situations, the spectrogram gives an excellent indication of the time-frequency properties of the signal. However, other situations exist where it does not represent the signal in a sufficient manner because there is an inherent trade-off between time and frequency resolution. If the signal changes in a rapid fashion, a short-duration analysis window must be used with a corresponding loss in frequency resolution. Conversely, if a long-duration analysis window is used, frequency resolution will be good but time resolution will be degraded.

Another TFR which gives excellent results for many signals is the Wigner distribution:

$$\text{TFR}_{\text{WD}}(t, f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} s\left(t + \frac{\tau}{2}\right) s^*\left(t - \frac{\tau}{2}\right) e^{-j2\pi f \tau} d\tau \quad (2)$$

The Wigner distribution is capable of tracking transient and time-varying signals that exhibit rapid changes of frequency structure. However, for machinery applications, the Wigner distribution suffers from the problem of cross-term interference that is generated by each pair of frequency components as a result of the quadratic nature of the distribution.

The Wigner distribution and spectrogram are members of a general class of functions defined by Cohen [1] as:

$$\text{TFR}_{\text{COHEN}}(t, f; \phi) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} s\left(t' + \frac{\tau}{2}\right) s^*\left(t' - \frac{\tau}{2}\right) \times \phi(v, \tau) \exp[j2\pi(-v t - \tau f + v t')] dt' d\tau dv \quad (3)$$

where $\phi(v, \tau)$ is a kernel function that determines the properties of the TFR. The advantage of this formulation is that desirable properties of a representation are simply reflected in the properties of the kernel. Much of the recent work in this area involves designing kernels that produce TFR's with desirable properties.

Various researchers have attempted to define properties that are desirable in a TFR [2, 3]. Examples of these properties are nonnegativity, artifact suppression, and time and frequency support properties (the TFR has a zero value in time and frequency whenever the signal has a zero value). In addition, summing the energy of a TFR over all frequencies should yield the temporal energy density of the signal,

and summing the energy of a TFR over all time should yield the spectral energy density (the time and frequency marginal properties, respectively).

For the case of general machinery analysis, artifact suppression is especially important to ensure that the information presented in the TFR corresponds to physically interpretable features in the signal. Also, frequency support is of significance for comparison purposes if the TFR is used to supplement analysis of narrowband power spectral levels. A kernel function [4] that supports these properties is given by:

$$\phi_{\text{ck}}(v, \tau) = |\tau| \frac{\sin(\pi v \tau)}{\pi v \tau} \quad (4)$$

which is known as the cone-kernel because of the shape of its region of support in the two-dimensional time domain. The cone-kernel TFR provides an excellent representation of the time and frequency structure of the machinery signal.

Additional research is underway to design TFR's that provide a true energy density interpretation of a signal [5]. Proper TFR's that have signal-dependent kernels have been shown to exist by Cohen and Posch [6]. Because these representations are nonnegative and satisfy the marginals, they could be used to compare energy density values (signal energy per unit time and frequency) with established reference values for each particular machine. This would also enable trending of data for specific machines.

Analysis of Machinery Data

The data used in this survey consisted of several sets of marine machinery data taken approximately three months apart. Representative machines included various pumps, fans, blowers, distilling plant machinery, refrigeration compressors, motor-generators, and turbines. The data was acquired using an accelerometer-based digital audio tape recorder system with a sample rate of 48 KHz. Before final processing, the data was listened to aurally and examined with a spectrum analyzer, oscilloscope, and spectrogram generator. Although the initial data set was processed with several TFR's, including the Wigner distribution, Choi-Williams, Cohen's Born-Jordan, and cone-kernel TFR's, the final comparisons were accomplished using the spectrogram and cone-kernel TFR.

The TFR's performed as expected when processing test signals; however, a relative degree of uncertainty existed with regard to expected results of processing the machinery data. This uncertainty was a result of the difficulty associated with accurately modelling the vibration characteristics of the machine. Even a

relatively simple machine is a complex system with multiple resonances and sources of excitations. In addition, the response of the machine is dependent not only on the time history of the excitation, but also on the spatial distribution of the excitation force and the geometry of the machinery components that respond to the excitation. The representative time-frequency plots in figures 1, 2, and 3 illustrate this complexity as opposed to the traditional simplified description of the machine as a lumped parameter system of certain mass and stiffness which experiences a sinusoidal excitation.

Figure 1(a) is a narrowband spectrogram of an axial fan running at constant speed taken over a time period of about 0.75 second. Figure 1(b) is a cone-kernel TFR of the same data. The power spectrum of the fan indicated that there were no obvious potential problems associated with the fan. In figure 1(b), note the modulation pattern (denoted by the arrow) at a bearing-related frequency of about 180 Hz. This pattern does not appear in the spectrogram as a result of the time-frequency resolution trade-off that results from the previously-mentioned analysis window. Although the origin has not been specifically determined, this modulation appears in the time-frequency spectra of other machines, including hydraulic pumps.

Figure 1(c) is a cone-kernel TFR of the same fan taken after a time period of three months when the machine was identified by power spectral analysis as having a potentially defective bearing. In addition to a greater degree of broadband energy, notice that modulation of the single tone in figure 1(b) has evolved into two discrete frequencies (arrow). These characteristics were observed for two similar fans with potential bearing problems. A point of interest is the manner in which broadband energy is depicted by each of these methods. In figures 1(a) and 1(b), note the difference in representation between the spectrogram and cone-kernel TFR of the energy associated with a suspected resonance region in the vicinity around 390 Hz. The notion of what constitutes a correct representation of broadband energy is a topic that requires further study.

Figure 2 represents a 0.5 second cone-kernel TFR of a motor-generator set with a spalled bearing. Although a few bearing-related frequency "lines" (arrow) are evident, the most obvious feature is the broadband energy that exists throughout the time-frequency domain. In this case, large bands of energy were observed to shift over time intervals of about 0.1 to 0.3 second. When the machine was monitored three months earlier, the broadband shifting was evident, but over a time interval two to three times as long. These two examples are illustrative of the different manner in which bearing problems may be manifested.

As a final example, figure 3 represents a 0.75 second cone-kernel TFR of a motor-generator set that has a bearing-related frequency that is coincident with a suspected machine resonance frequency at about 185 Hz. Note the time-varying nature (arrow) of the broadband energy in this region. A similar phenomenon has been observed with suspected fan stall and impeller problems. It is often difficult to assess whether these problems are impeller or bearing-related when using conventional power spectral analysis.

Summary

Time-frequency representations may be used to supplement conventional power spectral analysis if defects of constant-speed machines have a time dependence that can be observed over a period of a few seconds. Features that have been observed in the time-frequency spectra of constant-speed machines include various forms of modulation and time-varying broadband energy. Although the spectrogram is useful to assess general time-varying characteristics, new representations such as the cone-kernel TFR are capable of extracting additional information from the signal.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to thank Professor Leon Cohen of Hunter College, City University of New York, David Dean of NSWC Detachment Puget Sound, and Professor Les Atlas, Dr. Pat Loughlin, and Dr. Jim Pitton of the University of Washington for their assistance.

References

- [1] L. Cohen, "Time-frequency distributions - A review," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 77, no.7, pp. 941-981, 1989.
- [2] J. Jeong, and W. Williams, "Kernel design for reduced interference distributions," *IEEE Trans. Sig. Proc.*, vol 40, no. 2, pp. 402-412, 1992.
- [3] P. Loughlin, J. Pitton, L. Atlas, "Bilinear time-frequency representations: new insights and properties," *IEEE Trans. Sig. Proc.*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp.750-767, 1993.
- [4] Y. Zhao, L. Atlas, and R. Marks II, "The use of cone-shaped kernels for generalized time-frequency representation of nonstationary signals," *IEEE Trans. ASSP*, vol. 38, no. 7, pp. 1084-1091, 1990.
- [5] P. Loughlin, "Time-frequency energy density functions: theory and synthesis," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Washington, Seattle, Wa., 1992.
- [6] L. Cohen and T. Posch, "Positive time-frequency distribution functions," *IEEE Trans. ASSP*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 31-38, 1985.

Figure 1: TFRs of axial fan data. (a) Spectrogram (b) Cone-Kernel (c) Cone-Kernel of same fan with developing bearing problem.

Figure 2: Cone-Kernel TFR of motor-generator set with bearing problem.

Figure 3: Cone-Kernel TFR of motor-generator set with bearing frequency that coincides with machine resonance frequency.